

STATISTICAL STUDY OF THE STATUS AND DYNAMICS OF PRODUCTION IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

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Agriculture is an important source of growth of the national economy, the associated industry, the main engine of development of industries, production and services in rural areas. The head of our state Sh. In a speech on the occasion of the Day of Agricultural Workers on December 9, 2017, Mirziyoyev said, "... it is no exaggeration to say that the farmer is a strong pillar of life, a strong pillar of livelihood."

Ensuring the food security of the country depends on the sustainable development of this sector.

During the years of independence, large-scale measures have been taken to implement economic reforms in the agricultural sector of the country, aimed at the introduction of market relations and the development of private ownership. As a

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the state and dynamics of the economic development of the agricultural sector in terms of forms of management, the factors influencing them, as well as the place of the region's economy in the country's economic indicators.

result, the share of the non-governmental sector in the structure of agricultural production is currently 99.9%. Although the share of agriculture in the gross domestic product will be 25.1% in 2020, a decrease of 13.3% compared to 2000, production in this area is growing rapidly. This is evidenced by the fact that in 2020 the volume of agricultural production amounted to 250250.6 billion soums, which is almost 1.6 times more than in 2010 (Table 1). This is much higher than in the CIS countries. accordance with the 3 priorities of the Decree of the President of Uzbekistan PF-60 "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" dated January 28, 2022, 5 percent delivery "[1].

The main economic entities in the agricultural sector of the republic are

farmers and dehqan (personal assistant) farms and organizations engaged in agricultural activities. The share of these entities in the production of agricultural products by 2020 will be 28.2; 67.4 and 4.4 percent, respectively, and in 2015, 30.7; 66.9 and 2.4 percent, respectively (Table 2).

The reason for the decline in the share of agricultural production in farms is the creation of industrial products (works, services).

In 2020, the share of the agricultural sector in the total volume of agricultural production in the country will be 49.5%, the livestock sector - 50.5%, in farms and dehqan farms - 52.0 and 4.9%, 42.3 and 92.0%, respectively. reached The share of agriculture in the total value of agricultural

production by economic categories in farms and dehqan farms in recent years (2021) increased, reaching 52.6 and 41.1%, respectively. At present, the bulk of livestock products are produced on farms [4].

According to preliminary data, the growth rate of agricultural production in 2021 will reach 103.6%, in current prices - 302524.9 billion (259259.6 billion in 2020). The share of agricultural and livestock products was 49.9% and 50.1%, respectively, and 29.2% of agricultural products were created on farms and 65.9% on dehqan (personal assistant) farms [5].

Statistical analysis of the main indicators of agriculture of the Republic

Table 1

Indicators	Years											2020 compared to 2010,%
	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	
Arable land for agricultural crops, thousand hectares	3708.4	3601.6	3628.1	3658.6	3678.2	3694.2	3706.7	3474.5	3396.0	3309.4	3373,1	91.0
Agricultural production, bln. sum :												
a) current ba hoda	30856.7	45285.9	55750,0	66435,3	81794.3	99604,6	115599,2	148199.3	187425,6	216283,1	250250,6	x
b) At the 2020 price	160197.9	170130.2	182379,6	194416,6	206664,8	219271,4	233085.5	235416,4	235887,2	243671.5	250250,6	156.2
Including :												
farming	86477.9	90715,3	97156,1	103082.6	109164.5	115168,6	121733,2	119542.0	114521,2	120018.2	123858.8	143.2
animal husbandry	72898.7	78730,6	84556.7	90729.4	96808.2	103488.0	110732,1	115272,2	121842.7	123792,2	126391.8	173.4
Product volume growth rate (% compared to last year)												
in agriculture - total	106.3	106.2	107.2	106.6	106.3	106.1	106.3	101.0	100.2	103.3	102.7	156.2
in agriculture	105.9	104.9	107.1	106.1	105.9	105.5	105.7	98.2	95.8	104.8	103.2	143.2
in animal husbandry	106.9	108.0	107.4	107.3	106.7	106.9	107.0	104.1	105.7	101.6	102.1	173.4

x) Ўзбекистон Давлат статистика қўмитаси маълумотлари асосида муаллиф тамонидан ҳисобланган.

the period 2010-2020, which is analyzed in the country, we can see that the sown area of agricultural crops decreased by 335.3 thousand hectares or 9.0%. This is due to the fact that land users do not strictly adhere to agrotechnology, the emergence of abandoned lands due to increased salinity of arable land, the sale of land by farmers to citizens (for the construction of private plots). The analysis of the data presented in Table 1 shows that in the period under review, the growth rate of total agricultural production was 156.2%, and for agricultural and livestock products - 143.2% and 173.4%, respectively. The high price parity of products in animal husbandry indicates that this sector has a relatively large growth rate. Accordingly, the growth rate of livestock production for 2010-2020 was 111.0% and 121.1%, respectively, for agriculture as a whole. It should be noted that in recent years there have been structural shifts in agricultural production. If the share of the agricultural sector in the structure of agricultural products in current prices was 58.7 and 55.6% in 2010 and 2015, by 2020 it was 49.5%, which is 9.2 percentage points lower than in 2010. As a result, the share of livestock products increased by 9.2 percentage points.

Today, the volume of products in the agricultural sector in our country is

determined in the calculation process by a new sector, which is generally called "Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries." The sector generated 25.1 percent of GDP in 2020 and 27.1 percent of gross value added, which in 2017 was 28.6 percent and 32.2 percent, respectively. The share of industry in the gross value added of industries

was 21.1% in 2017 and 27.4% in 2020. These indicators indicate that our republic is becoming an industrial-agrarian country.

In general, the volume of agricultural production in 2020 increased by 56.2% compared to 2010, with an average annual growth rate of 4.6%.

It should be noted that farms have a number of advantages over other forms of management. In their activities, there are no serious problems entering and exiting the market; Economic flexibility and flexibility in production create ample opportunities for rapid adaptation to changes in market conditions; reliance on private ownership increases resource efficiency; as a non-financially dependent economy, develops production mainly at its own expense; farms fully meet the requirements of a market economy in terms of their socio-economic nature and principles of management .

Table 2

Level and dynamics of production in the country by economic categories

Years	Product size (In 2020 estimates), billion soums	Growth rate (Compared to 2015),%	Share in gross agricultural output,%
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	On farms	On farms	Agricultural organizations	On farms	On farms	Agricultural organizations	On farms	On farms	Agricultural organizations
2015	68858,8	145532,0	4789.6	100.0	100.0	100.0	30.7	66.9	2.4
2016	70580.2	157465,6	4842.3	102.5	108.2	101.1	29.7	68.0	2.3
2017	65286.7	164551,6	5074.7	94.8	113.1	105.9	29.3	68.4	2.3
2018	60781.9	168336,3	6378.9	88.3	115.7	133.2	26.0	71.2	2.8
2019	67164,0	166989,6	89559.5	97.5	114.7	187.0	27.9	68.3	3.8
2020	69313,3	169828.4	10612.8	100.7	116.7	221.6	28.2	67.4	4.4

Source: Calculated by the author on the basis of data from the State Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan.

In 2020, farms will produce 81.9% of the gross yield of cereals and legumes, 86.5% of cotton, 48.5% of melons, 40.5% of fruits, 41.3% of grapes and 35.2% of vegetables. plays a huge role in the development of the industry. However, the share of farms in livestock production remains low.

Research shows that there are principles of correlation and interaction between the growth of agricultural production on farms and the level of development of their property relations in relation to property, yield and income. This is because the more each farmer increases the volume of production and income, the greater his profitability.

However, there are a number of issues that need to be addressed in order to further develop the production activities of farms. These, in turn, have an impact on the efficiency of agricultural production. In particular, farms are not adequately equipped with mechanization, and at the same time the quality of various services provided to them by the relevant

enterprises is often low and expensive [2]. Despite radical changes in the agricultural sector, the level of investment is low, and its share in total investment in the country's economy in 2020 was 7.0%.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 28, 2019 No PF-5853 "On approval of the Strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" it is expedient to widely introduce science-based methods of further development of clusters and cooperation.

The state and dynamics of economic development in Kashkadarya region in recent years have been studied as an object of observation.

The analysis of the main economic indicators of the Republic and Kashkadarya region, presented in Table 3, provides a clearer picture of the state of the regional economy in the national economy. Under the influence of natural-climatic and demographic factors, in 2015, the gross regional product of the region amounted to 7.8% of GDP, while by 2021 this figure decreased by 1.8%. During the 7 years of analysis, the country's GDP grew by 34.8% and the average annual growth rate was

5.1%, while the gross regional product of Kashkadarya region grew by 25.4% and the average annual growth rate was 3.8%. [3].

The change in the volume of gross domestic product and gross regional product depends in many respects on the volume of investments attracted and mastered in the economy. The share of investments in the regional economy in the country has a declining trend, falling from 13.2% in 2015 to 6.6%. This, of course, can be explained by the more active investment movement of the economy in other regions than in Kashkadarya region.

Kashkadarya region ranks 5th in the country in terms of agricultural production,

and in 2021 compared to 2015 the growth rate of production in this sector was 113.8%, and the average annual growth rate was 102.2%. At the national level, these figures were 118.2 and 102.8 percent, respectively (Table 3).

Kashkadarya region, the share of arable land used in the cultivation of agricultural products is the largest in the country, ie 13.4% (2020), the share of regional gross agricultural output in the country over the past 7 years is 9.1-9.7. percent remains.

Table 3

The share and dynamics of the main economic indicators of Kashkadarya region in the country's economy

№	Indicators	Years							2021 compared to 2015,%
		2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021 ^{x)}	
1	Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth rate,%	107.2	105.9	104.4	105.4	105.7	101.9	107.4	134.8
2	Gross regional product (GRP) growth rate,%	106.6	105.6	103.5	102.0	101.8	102.7	107.6	125.4
3	Share of GRP in GDP,%	7.8	7.9	6.8	6.3	6.1	5.9	6.0	-
4	The share of investments in the regional economy in the country,%	13.2	14.3	15.5	13.3	12.5	9.8	6.6	-
5	Growth rate of gross agricultural output of the country,%	106.1	106.3	101.0	100.2	103.3	102.7	103.6	118.2
6	Regional Gross	106.1	106.5	103.3	96.5	101.4	103.7	101.9	113.8

^{x)} Preliminary data.

	Agricultural Product Growth Rate,%								
7	Share of regional gross agricultural output in the country,%	9.1	9.4	9.7	9.2	9.2	9.5	9.4	-
8	Progress coefficients, times: a) GRP (2 q: 1 q)	0.994	0.997	0.991	0.968	0.963	1,008	1,002	0.930
	b) By regional agricultural production (6 q: 5 q)	1,000	1,002	1,023	0.963	0.982	1,010	0.984	0.963

Source: Calculated by the author on the basis of data from the State Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan and the Statistics Department of Kashkadarya region.

It should be noted that the low share of irrigated lands in agricultural lands in the region is 23.5% (01.01.2021) and the availability of dry and conditionally irrigated lands. Of course, it should also be noted that factors such as the whims of nature and climatic conditions have a negative impact.

In order to increase the efficiency of agricultural land and increase production, it is expedient to widely introduce advanced modern innovative technologies and agro-cluster systems in the agricultural sector.

The coefficients of improvement shown in Table 3 are 93.0% in terms of GRP and 96.3% in terms of regional agricultural production. relative to 1,075 and 1,039 times, respectively. Of course, it is necessary to take into account the methodological basis of the indicators calculated by country and region.

The analysis of the volume of products produced in the agricultural and livestock sectors of the regional agricultural sector in 2015-2021 shows that there have been significant changes in the sector. In particular, the share of agriculture in the gross agricultural output decreased from 44.5% to 39.2%, and the share of livestock increased from 55.5% to 60.8% (Table 4).

Table 4

Changes in the share of agricultural production in Kashkadarya region by sectors and forms of management

Indicators	Years						
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Gross agricultural output, bln.	9089.0	10863.6	14360,6	17206.5	19933.9	23777.8	28342.6

sum							
Including% :							
-agricultural products	44.5	41.8	46.0	40.4	40.0	38.8	39.2
- Livestock products	55.5	58.2	54.0	59.6	60.0	61.2	60.8
The share of forms of management in agricultural production,%:							
- on farms	28.7	28.2	30.8	25.2	26.1	24.9	26.2
-in farms (personal assistants)	69.9	70.2	67.6	72.8	71.6	71.8	70.7
- In organizations engaged in agricultural activities	1.4	1.6	1.6	2.0	2.3	3.3	3.1

Source: Calculated by the author on the basis of data from the Kashkadarya regional statistics department.

When analyzing the volume of gross agricultural output of Kashkadarya region by forms of management, it was found that there are certain trends. In 2021, 26.2% of the total agricultural output in the region was grown on farms, 70.7% on dehqan farms and 3.1% on organizations engaged in agricultural activities. At the same time, in 2021, the share of farms decreased compared to 2015, and the share of other categories of farms had an upward trend (Table 4).

We observe that in 2015-2021, the share of oscillations in the share of farms was mainly 59.0-64.5%, in farms 34.3-39.5% and in agricultural organizations 2.1-3.4%. possible.

In conclusion, the development of medium and long-term strategies for the future development of the agricultural sector of the country and Kashkadarya region, taking into account the trends identified in the analysis , will be important in the development of the sector on a scientific basis.

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